

Equilibrium Studies on Interactions of Transition and Rare Earth Ions with Substituted β -Diketones

P. D. SAWALAKHE^{*a} and M. L. NARWADE^b

^aDepartment of Chemistry, College of Engineering Badnera-444 701

^bDepartment of Chemistry, Vidarbha Mahavidyalaya, Amravati-444 601

Manuscript received 6 April 1994, revised 14 September 1994, accepted 15 September 1994

β -Diketones have been found to possess various biological activities¹. Especially, methoxy and hydroxy β -diketones are of pharmaceutical importance². So far the interactions of metals with β -hydroxydiketones (1-3) containing methyl and methoxy groups have not been reported. In this communication the stability constants of Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Pr^{III}, Nd^{III} and Sm^{III} complexes with 1-(2-hydroxyphenyl-3-phenyl)-1,3-propanedione (1), 1-(2-hydroxy-5-methylphenyl)-3-phenyl-1,3-propanedione (2) and 1-(2-hydroxy-5-methylphenyl)-3-(4-methoxy)-phenyl-1,3-propanedione (3) have been reported.

Results and Discussion

The values of $\bar{n}_H$ show that the ligands behave as monoprotic acid due to deprotonation of phenolic OH. The dissociation of proton from enol tautomer could not be approached since the dissociation constants are below 9.5 and the readings were erratic in this region. The pK values of these ligands are found to be lower than that of 2-hydroxyacetophenone (9.98) and phenol (10.50)³. The lowering of pK values of present ligands than the parent suggests the increase in acid strength due to steric hinderance caused by the side-chain. The pK value of the diketone 2, is slightly higher than that of 1. This suggests decrease in acid strength of 2 due to the presence of CH₃ group at position-5 in aryl part. The lower pK_a value of ligand 2 than 1 shows how deprotonation is favoured by the presence of CH₃ group at the *para*-position of OH group in aryl part. The decrease in acid strength of ligand 2 may be probably due to electron-releasing nature of substituted CH₃ group. The lowering of the pK value of the ligand 3 is attributed to the presence of OCH₃ group in the side-chain. The electron-releasing influence of the OCH₃

group may be compensated due to the resonance stabilisation of aryl ring in side-chain and the presence of electron-releasing CH₃ group in phenolic ring. Thus increase in acid strength of diketone 3 indicates that lone-pair of oxygen is more operative than inductive effect of OCH₃ group.

The values of $\bar{n} > 2$ were not obtained in any system. Similarly, the difference between log K₁ and K₂ values is less than 2.5. This indicates simultaneous formation of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes. The linear relationship between log K and pK values suggests identical binding sites in all the ligands. The observed slope values of rare earth metal complexes (1.00–1.17) are found to be higher than those of transition metal complexes (0.69–0.97). This is justifiable in the light of the suggestion by Jones. The slope values are almost unity. This suggests that the free energy of ligand may be compensated with the free energy of metal complex.

The log K values show that the rare earth metal ions form more stable complexes with these ligands

TABLE I—PROTON-LIGAND AND METAL-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF THE DIKETONES (1-3) WITH METAL IONS

Metal ion	1		2		3	
	log K ₁	log K ₂	log K ₁	log K ₂	log K ₁	log K ₂
H ⁺	8.50	-	8.95	-	6.90	-
Co ^{II}	8.65	7.75	8.00	7.10	5.30	5.00
Ni ^{II}	9.70	8.30	9.00	7.70	7.20	5.10
Cu ^{II}	9.25	8.35	8.55	7.60	7.05	6.05
Pr ^{III}	10.80	8.50	9.80	7.95	8.20	6.10
Nd ^{III}	9.80	8.85	9.10	8.20	8.10	6.50
Sm ^{III}	10.52	9.25	10.35	9.60	8.50	7.30

than the transition metal ions. The log K values of the rare earth metal chelates differ slightly from each other, indicating the lanthanide contraction. The stability of the rare earth metal chelates follows the order: $\text{Pr}^{\text{III}} > \text{Nd}^{\text{III}} < \text{Sm}^{\text{III}}$. Such difference in the trend of stability constants is not uncommon in case of lanthanides⁴ and this may be due to varying degree of stabilisation arising out of interactions of $4f$ -metal orbitals with ligand field⁵.

The stabilities of the transition metal chelates follow the order: $\text{Cu}^{\text{I}} < \text{Ni}^{\text{I}} > \text{Co}^{\text{I}}$. Though the sequence differs from the Mellor-Maley which has been found to hold almost universally for oxygen and nitrogen donor ligands or Irving Williams natural order of stability, it is in conformity with the stability order reported for the chelates of these metals with several monothio- β -diketones studied so far⁶.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. The ligands (1-3) were prepared and purified by the methods described earlier⁷. 1,4-Dioxane was purified by the standard method⁸. The metal ions used were in the form of their nitrates. An Elico LI-120 pH meter was used. Standard NaOH and 1 M NaClO_4 solutions were prepared in double-distilled water. The titrations of (i) $1.04 \times 10^{-2} M$ HClO_4 ; (ii) (i) + $2 \times 10^{-3} M$ ligand and (iii) (ii) + $4.02 \times 10^{-4} M$ metal ion solutions against standard carbonate-free NaOH solution (0.104 M) were

carried out by Calvin-Bjerrum pH-titration technique in 70% dioxane-water mixture at $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$ and 0.1 M ionic strength (maintained with 1 M NaClO_4). The total volume of each of the mixtures was made upto 50 ml so that the solutions were 70% (v/v) with respect to dioxane. All the titrations were carried out in the environment of oxygen-free nitrogen gas. The values of pK and log K were evaluated by the procedure of Irving and Rossotti.

References

1. S. C. KUSHAWAIA, DINAKAR and J. B. LAI, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1967, **5**, 82.
2. C. W. WILSON and D. E. LLOYD, *J. Pharmacol. Exp. Ther.*, 1949, **95**, 399.
3. P. SYKES, "A Guide Book to Mechanism in Organic Chemistry". Orient Longmans, London, 1965, p. 45.
4. J. L. BEAR, G. R. CHIOPPIN and J. V. QUAGLIANO, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1962, **24**, 1601; 1963, **25**, 578.
5. L. K. A. STAVELY and T. RANDALL, *Discuss. Faraday Soc.*, 1958, **26**, 157.
6. S. E. LIVINGSTONE, *J. Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1971, **7**, 59; M. COX and DARKIN, *J. Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1971, **7**, 29.
7. P. N. WADODKAR and M. G. MARATHLY, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1972, **10**, 142.
8. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry", Longmans, London, 1966.